

CHINESE ACTORS AND ACTRESSES AND THE FILM INDUSTRY IN CHINA

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Annotation: This article contains information about the actors of the Chinese industry. Here you can read the biography of three of the most famous actors in China. Also a few facts about them and about their achievements and awards. And how they succeeded on their difficult path to fame. What difficulties have they gone through and about their successes to date. Moreover, I want to tell you their ratings at the world level.

Key words. Jackie Chan, Dylan Wang ,Zhang Xincheng, China, Hong Kong, Beijing, Jinzhou.

There are many actors in the Chinese industry. Every year the Chinese industry grows and occupies the whole world. They showed their acting skills and won the hearts of people. In this article I will talk about the most popular actors and my favorite actors.

Dylan Wang, a film actor from China, managed to become the star of a TV series called "The Fallen Garden", which was recognized by a large number of fans around the world. The debate about the reasons for such popularity has not subsided to this day. Of course, I watched this play, and I also like this game. I suggest you watch this. The birthplace of the future stars of the film industry is the provincial capital near Sichuan, Chinese territory. The real name of the movie star is Van Hedi. He graduated from high school and then became a student at the Southwest College of Civil Aviation in Sichuan Province. Dylan managed to become a flight attendant because his family insisted on it. At the beginning of her creative career, Van Heidi

had to study and work as a presenter and model at the same time. His debut was the TV series "Meteor Garden", where he became popular. Other plays by Dylan Wong: "Let Go of the Night", "Live Rationally", etc. Every year he becomes more and more popular.

My favorite actor is Jackie Chan. Chan was born in Hong Kong, China, and his stage name is Son Lung or Kit Cheng Lung. Jackie Chan, sometimes known as Fong Xiling; born April 7, 1954) is a Hong Kong actor, stuntman, film director, film producer, screenwriter, stunt and fight scene director, singer, philanthropist, martial artist. Goodwill Ambassador of the United Nations Children's Fund. Knights of the British Empire is the chief director of Changchun Film Studio, the oldest film studio in China. Chan is one of the most popular action heroes in the world. He is known for his technical fighting style, comedic talent and the use of various "tactics" in combat. He has appeared in more than 100 films and is one of the most famous Asian actors in the world. In addition to films, he is also engaged in singing - he has been singing and releasing albums in many films since the 1980. He received an honorary Academy Award for his contribution to the art of cinema. Jackie Chan's favorite movie is "Karate Boy".

Zhang Xincheng was born in August 24, 1995. Also known by his English name Steven Zhang, is a Chinese actor. Zhang was born and raised in Jingzhou, China. As a child, he aspired to become a professional dancer and eventually moved to Beijing in 2008 to enroll in the affiliated secondary school Beijing Dance Academy. Zhang took first place in the college entrance exams in 2014 in several courses offered by China's leading performing arts colleges, such as the Central Academy of Drama, Beijing Film Academy, People's Liberation Army Art Academy and Shanghai Theater Academy. Subsequently, he studied at the Central Academy of Drama and received a bachelor's degree in musical theater. His first major role was the role of Lin Yang in the school drama "My Friends Huckleberry" (2017). Zhang is best known for his roles as Li Yubin in the sports drama Roll into Love and He Ziqu in the family drama Forward, both of which aired in 2020 and

earned him several awards for his work in the same year. In 2013, Zhang debuted in the short film "School Bus". In 2014, he released two singles; "Be Here for You" as the soundtrack to the film "The Story of Ho Jinye" and "Believe that Love Still Exists" as the soundtrack to the web series "Emergency Room with a Broken with my heart ." He has starred in several short films, and in 2015 signed a contract with the entertainment company EE-Media. In 2016, Zhang starred in his first television drama "Love Shuttle, Millennium", where he attracted attention with his performance. In 2017, Zhang starred in the critically acclaimed campus web drama My Friends Huckleberry. He won the Best New Actor Award at the iQiyi All-Star Carnival for his performance. In 2018, Zhang starred in the esports drama The Strongest Men of God .In 2019, Zhang starred in the youth historical drama "Young Blood". In 2020, Zhang, along with Janice Wu, starred in the popular sports romantic drama "Skate in Love " , playing a student hockey player. He then starred in the musical romantic drama Symphony's Romance , adapted from the Japanese manga Nodame Cantabile ; a brilliant conductor is playing. Zhang also played the lead role and helped produce the family drama "Forward" Forbes China included him in its list of "30 people under 30" for 2020, which included 30 influential people under the age of 30 who have achieved significant influence in their fields. In 2021, Zhang participated in the sixth season of "Star Detective"; on February 28, he was awarded the Weibo "Enterprising Artist of the Year" award at Sina Weibo Night 2020 in Shanghai; in May, he starred in the series "Abyss" with Xinbo Fu; on June 17, Zhang co-starred with Liang Jie in the light love comedy "The Day of Becoming You"; on September 8, Zhang co-starred with Cai Wenjing in a commercial war drama about the Republic of China., Zhang Xuehan, etc. "Light" was broadcast on satellite television in Hunan Province. On October 16, Taihe Maitian Music Group jointly launched a large-scale album of the theme music of the documentary "Forbidden City". The announced line-up of the singer includes Zhang Xincheng. In December, he joined Hunan Satellite TV's New Year's Gala 2021-2022 and performed "Red Ling" with Chinese music artist Fan Jinlong; New Year's Eve party".

Every day there are different movies and TV series that have different meanings. The producer is trying to improve the quality and significance of the film. See what choice you have. In their own way, all the films and actors are very *good*.

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